

Gender and Social Sciences Involvement in Technology Development Projects in Energy (in Turkish)

Theme: Energy, European Research Area and SSH Aspects

Pınar Derin Güre

METU Economics and ODTÜ GÜNAM

Moderator: Gülsevım Evsel

Live Seminar Time and Date: 12:00-13:00 (Turkish time / GMT + 3)

Friday, May 20, 2022

Register at: <https://forms.gle/i5UuBeNJFkHjZS2PA>

Moderation: Asst. Prof. Dr. Gülsevım Evsel

Registration for live seminar closes at 20:00, Thursday, 19 May 2022: To receive the link to the live seminar you must register by 20:00, Thursday 19 May 2022.

Abstract: Even with the most sophisticated and advanced technologies, technological innovations in energy can fail to deliver results if society would not accept them. Under specific circumstances, changes in energy technologies might have certain economic and social benefits as well as costs to society. By detecting these, the socio-economic research on energy can put light on proper energy transition strategies for society, the industry, and policymakers. In the last years, European Commission, as well as TÜBİTAK, started to emphasize the role of Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) involvement in Technological Projects. This talk will aim to put the challenges, barriers as well as benefits (the low-hanging fruits) for the participation of SSH research on technological innovations. This talk will also aim to discuss the role of gender in technology development projects. Horizon Europe made it mandatory for the institutions to have a gender equality plan (GEP) before applying for Project funding. In addition to this, it became compulsory to include the gender dimension in the R&I content under Horizon Europe applications. The range of GEP and probable gender dimensions in energy R&I and its potential impact on Turkish research institutions will be discussed.

Speaker:

Pınar Derin-Güre is an Assoc. Professor in the Department of Economics in METU. She holds B.S. and MS. in economics degrees from METU (2001 and 2003) and Ph.D. in Economics Degree (2009) from Boston University, USA. She had been a visiting scholar at Dartmouth College, Boston University, and Brandeis University in the U.S. and held lectures in Development Economics, Macroeconomics, and Financial Markets. She is interested in Development economics, focusing on the economics of immigration, tax policy, and renewable energy focusing on solar and geothermal energy. She has been a part of the Horizon 2020 GeoSmart Project and is the Project leader in a national research project (Tübitak 1004) on Socioeconomic Impacts of Solar Energy

About SolarTwins-TEKPOL Seminars: The path to a prosperous, sustainable, and secure Turkey includes a Clean Energy Transition (CET) and Green Economy Transition (GET). Many of the largest challenges to be solved to realize these transitions lie at the intersection of technology and policy. Some of these challenges are unique to a specific technology, while others are cross-cutting challenges that underpin the competitiveness of Turkey's Research and Innovation (R&I) ecosystem. This SolarTwins-TEKPOL Pizza Seminar series aims to provide a scientific forum to increase awareness of these challenges and contribute to the co-creation of solutions to overcome these challenges. This series is designed as a part of SolarTwins Project Joint Research Line 9: Social Aspects of Sustainable Energy Transitions

About SolarTwins: SolarTwins is a European Union Horizon 2020 (H2020) project coordinated by ODTÜ-GÜNAM through METU with CIEMAT-PSA (Spain) and DLR (Germany) as partners. The objectives of the SolarTwins project are to

1. Step-up the scientific excellence of the Concentrating Solar Thermal (CST) Research Division ODAK of ODTÜ-GÜNAM through capacity building activities in collaboration with the globally leading CST institutions CIEMAT-PSA and DLR.
2. Strengthen METU, ODTÜ-GÜNAM, and Turkey's horizontal Research and Innovation (R&I) Capacities.

About METU TEKPOL: Science and Technology Policy Studies (STPS) program was founded in 1997 at the Middle East Technical University with the explicit objective to supply science and technology policy related human capital for the government bodies, agencies and other related organizations and to conduct research in science, technology and innovation policy issues. It has organic relations with the Research Center for Science and Technology Policies. Education and research elements integrate under METU-TEKPOL. TEKPOL is the only academic unit in Turkey that concurrently coordinates education and research activities. It operates M.Sc. and Ph.D. programs in science technology policy studies at the Graduate School of Social Sciences. TEKPOL also conducts interdisciplinary research on science and technology policy issues with the aim of addressing societal challenges.

PROGRAMME:

Date	Speaker, Institution	Seminar Title
15 April 2022	Arda MEVLÜTOĞLU, Kubilay YILDIRIM and Semih AKÇOMAK	TOGG and Beyond (in Turkish) – Panel
22 April 2022	Onur Çağdaş ARTANTAŞ	Promotion of Green Electricity: Legal and Political Perspectives (in Turkish)
29 April 2022	Serdar TÜRKELİ	Technological change and non-intervention, novel indicators and non-measurement (in Turkish)
13 May 2022	Barbel EPP	Cost Trends for Commercial and Industrial Solar Heat
20 May 2022	Pınar DERİN GÜRE	Gender and social sciences involvement in technology development projects in energy (in Turkish)
27 May 2022	Şuhnaz YILMAZ ÖZBAĞCI	Energy Security Challenges: Assessing Turkey's Role in Changing Regional Dynamics (in Turkish)
3 June 2022	Derek BAKER	ODAK _{TR} : Concentrating Solar Thermal (CST) as a key enabling technology for Turkey's Clean Energy Transition.
10 June 2022	Christian OLTRA	Introducing SSH aspects of Energy Transitions
17 June 2022	Sara Banu AKKAŞ and Zelal ÖZDEMİR	METU in New European Research Area (in Turkish)
24 June 2022	Seven AĞIR	AgroPV Potential, Opportunities and Barriers in Turkey: A Preliminary Evaluation From Social Sciences Perspective (in Turkish)

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SolarTwins has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 856619.